

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN RURAL SMEs DEVELOPMENT: A CASE OF KWAZULU-NATAL

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Abstract

Digital entrepreneurship practices have emerged as major drivers of the growth and development of Small and Medium Enterprises. SMEs are making use of digital platforms to enhance their growth and development; nevertheless, there is limited research on the role played by digital entrepreneurship in the development of SMEs in rural areas of countries like South Africa. The study assessed the role of digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs' development in the KwaZulu-Natal Province of South Africa. The study was influenced by the quantitative research methodology, using a non-probability sampling technique to select the study respondents. The sample size of 383 owners and managers of rural SMEs was drawn from the three selected district municipalities in KZN, namely Harry Gwala, uMkhanyakude, and uMzinyathi. The collected data was analysed using inferential and descriptive statistics. Indications from the study findings revealed that the majority of the study respondents acknowledge that digital entrepreneurship practices are a catalyst for the development of rural SMEs. Over 70% of the study respondents articulated that the utilisation of digital platforms by SMEs in rural KZN has since improved operational efficiency, revenue streams and access to markets for the rural SMEs. Conclusions drawn from the study findings revealed that rural economic growth and development can be stimulated through the use of digital entrepreneurship by SMEs. The study recommends that there is a need for targeted support from technology service providers, policy makers and government agencies to enhance funding mechanisms, training and digital infrastructure tailored for the needs of the rural SMEs.

Keywords: Influence, Digital Entrepreneurship, SME Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary digital era, entrepreneurship is transformed by swift technological advancements, leading to the emergence of digital entrepreneurship (Usman et al., 2024). This evolving paradigm entails recognising novel opportunities in the digital domain, establishing and initiating digital enterprises, or converting conventional ones into digital (Mbhele and Beharry-Ramraj, 2024a). Digital entrepreneurs utilise digital technologies such as websites, mobile applications, social media platforms, e-marketplaces, cloud computing, and digital payment methods (Olalekan, 2024b).

Digital entrepreneurship in this study is viewed as the strategic application of digital technologies to day-to-day business operations (Sahut et al., 2021). It involves a wide range of activities, including creating online platforms and mobile applications, as well as utilising social media and digital marketing methods (Wilk et al., 2021). Digital entrepreneurship leverages technology to access global markets, disrupt and innovate conventional businesses with unparalleled efficiency and speed (Oyeyemi et al., 2024). The growth and development of the SMEs in rural areas is influenced by the quantifiable enhancement of their competitiveness, performance and sustainability.

Even though there is evidence of the potential benefits of digital platforms in the growth and development of SMEs, the integration of digital tools in rural SMEs is affected by constraints such as a lack of digital infrastructure as well as limited access to high-speed internet connections. These two aspects are crucial for the operation of digital companies (Philip and Williams, 2019). Digital entrepreneurship offers substantial opportunities for rural SME owners, especially in developing nations such as South Africa, facilitating innovation, market access, and economic growth (Olalekan, 2024a). By adopting digital entrepreneurship, owners of rural SMEs can tap into new prospects, cultivate a digitally driven future, and foster optimistic results.

Previous studies have emphasised the potential impact of digital entrepreneurship on rural economic development and business performance. Muhamad and Kusuma (2024) assert that the implementation of technology-driven business models facilitates the establishment of a more inclusive and sustainable economic system, hence positively influencing rural economic development and environmental sustainability on a larger scale.

Tengeh et al. (2023) contend that the adoption and deployment of digital technology can facilitate rural entrepreneurs in accessing national and international markets to enhance their profitability. Moreover, studies express that digital platforms enable SMEs to minimise operational costs, enhance consumer engagement, and expand their business's visibility beyond geographical limitations (Luz, 2025, Mhlongo et al., 2024). Nevertheless, scoping review on digital entrepreneurship mainly focuses on urban or developed contexts, with negligible empirical evidence regarding the experiences of rural SMEs in rural and developing contexts.

This study examines the context of KwaZulu-Natal, a province characterised by socio-economic inequalities, elevated unemployment rates, and inadequate rural infrastructure (Luo et al., 2023); it is essential to comprehend how digital entrepreneurship can facilitate inclusive and sustainable economic development. The study assessed the role of digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs in KwaZulu-Natal Province of South Africa. The study is significant in that it addresses a major research gap, supporting fair economic growth, offering insights that boost entrepreneurship in rural areas and drive digital inclusion in the underserved communities of South Africa.

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to assess the role of digital entrepreneurship on the development of rural SMEs in KwaZulu-Natal.

Objectives

- To assess the role of digital entrepreneurship on the development of rural SMEs in KwaZulu-Natal.
- To identify specific digital entrepreneurship practices that rural SMEs can adopt to improve their development in KwaZulu-Natal.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Role of Digital Entrepreneurship in Supporting the Development of Rural SMEs

Despite having limited access to essential services, poor infrastructural development and relatively low economic activities, rural areas have distinct structural and economic attributes that present entrepreneurial endeavours (Luo et al., 2023). Rural SMEs have both indirect and direct impacts on the local environment. Direct impacts include improved services, development and value addition of local products, and creation of employment in the rural areas. Indirect impacts include spill-over effects as well as the added value of the SMEs' business venture operating within the local area (Bhuiyan et al., 2024). Developing countries should take advantage of rural areas as a base for regional economic transformation, growth and development. This is made possible by developing a conducive rural ecosystem and entrepreneurial network system, which allows for important access to social opportunities, creative capital sources, mentorship, incubation and retail space (Berezhnoy et al., 2021).

In essence, rural entrepreneurship is similar to urban entrepreneurship; rural entrepreneurship involves the strategic use of unique and diversified resource combinations derived from non-agricultural and agricultural sectors. There is a strong connection between the social goals of rural development and the economic goals of an entrepreneur as compared to those of urban areas (Bollweg et al., 2020). Due to this, entrepreneurship in the rural areas significantly influences rural communities, is strongly linked to extended families and is typically centred on communities (Brahma and Dutta, 2020). Additionally, adaptability and resilience are the traits that are often demonstrated by entrepreneurs in rural areas who use their ingenuity and interpersonal relationships to overcome drawbacks specific to their rural areas (Bruce et al., 2020).

Over the past years, digital tools have been instrumental in the transformation of societies and economies. With the ease and increasing growth of the use of digital tools to support the activities of entrepreneurs, these digital tools have opened doors to unique and new opportunities for the promotion of rural entrepreneurship and the development of rural SMEs (Cárdenas et al., 2022). It is worth of consideration to note that digitalisation extends beyond services, manufacturing processes, products and production. Digitalisation encompasses a wide range of competencies such as growth management, marketing, promotional mix, supply chain management, business networking and international markets to gain a competitive edge (Chen, 2023). Especially within the rural area settings, digitalisation of the rural SMEs can help address challenges such as a lack of human capital and outsourcing of certain services. This enables young entrepreneurs and new start-ups to operate conveniently and more willingly in rural environments (Chopra et al., 2024). Some of the benefits of integrating digital technologies in rural SMEs include increased ability to engage with customers beyond their borders, great operational efficiency, improved productivity and administrative efficiency (Chuang, 2020). These benefits can be achieved through digital platforms such as e-commerce websites and social media.

The digitalisation of rural SMEs through digital entrepreneurship is crucial for the growth and development of rural SMEs, as this promotes business visibility and gives the rural businesses a competitive advantage in the market since the business will be known beyond their geographical boundaries (Dana et al., 2022). A report compiled by the World Economic Forum in 2023 revealed that rural SMEs with a strong digital strategy are in a better position to deal with diversity and economic slumps. Micro and small business ventures in rural areas are increasingly viewed as a means of generating sustainable and meaningful income as well as employment opportunities for those who are economically marginalised (Deel, 2023). Thus, leveraging digital platforms and tools among rural SMEs can help address the traditional barriers and foster economic sustainable development in rural communities.

However, access to digital technologies alone is not sufficient in helping rural SMEs to flourish if they are not equipped with sufficient skills and knowledge on how to utilise digital technologies in the growth and development of rural SMEs (Dwivedi et al., 2021). The rapid digital technological advancement of present rural SMEs with a unique opportunity to help these businesses address some of the traditional challenges they might experience, hence enabling them to compete with others in the global marketplace (Elia et al., 2020). Even though the advantages of digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs development are well documented, there is limited discussion of the challenges being experienced by rural SMEs in their attempt to adopt and integrate digital entrepreneurship (Elshaiekh et al., 2023). Nevertheless, despite the potential benefits of digital entrepreneurship, SMEs operating in rural areas are still experiencing major drawbacks in the form of digital exclusion due to a lack of digital literacy, high cost of data and poor digital infrastructure (Febrian et al., 2022, Franco et al., 2021, Harahap et al., 2023). These challenges cannot be solved by digital tools alone, as reviewed literature highlighted that digital entrepreneurship widens the gap between poor-resourced and better-resourced entrepreneurship in the event that systemic inequalities are not addressed.

2.2 Digital Practices to Support the Development of Rural SMEs in Kwazulu-Natal

2.2.1 Digitalisation of Customer Services

Customer service technology is a crucial digital practice which fosters the growth and development of rural SMEs. Rural SMEs can easily adopt and innovate their customer services by embracing digital entrepreneurship (Holzmann and Gregori, 2023). Embracing digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs is crucial for improving the sustainability and competitiveness of the business. Digital customer services include online interaction between the customers and the business as well as user experience, efficient support system and website designing (Hosen et al., 2021). Rural SMEs can easily connect with the global markets beyond their communities, hence transcending their geographic limitations if they embrace and integrate digital customer services in their daily business initiatives. Successful digital customer services provide easy-to-use, seamless and personalised experiences across the digital platforms. Complementary to that, digital customer service promotes the quality of products and services offered by the rural SMEs, hence fulfilling the distinct customer needs (Jamil et al., 2022).

The networking of suppliers and clients can be enhanced through the digital transformation of the rural SMEs. Digital transformation leads to the establishment of innovative business models for the rural SMEs; these business models will enhance products and services offered by the rural SMEs (Jayadatta, 2023). It is worth of consideration to note that adopting and integrating digital transformation in rural SMEs contributes to value addition and increased revenue for the business venture of the rural SMEs (Jehanne, 2023). Digital technologies such as online payment systems, e-commerce platforms and virtual consultations enable rural SMEs to offer more convenient and personalised services. These convenient and personalised services address the evolving expectations of the customers in the digital age (Katsikeas et al., 2020, Kergroach, 2021). Adopting and integrating digital customer service technologies is crucial for rural SMEs operating in KwaZulu-Natal since it will enhance their capacity, improve customer satisfaction and operational competencies. These improvements help rural SMEs in KwaZulu-Natal to sustain and scale their business initiatives in the long run (Khan et al., 2024, Lannone and Caruso, 2023). Nevertheless, digital customer service uptake is often affected by user resistance, lack of digital infrastructure and poor digital literacy skills among the customers and the SMEs in the rural communities.

2.2.2 Fostering Competitive Drive through Digital Practices

The adoption and integration of digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs fosters a competitive drive and stimulates the growth and development of rural SMEs. Digital technologies reshape the traditional ideas of business competitiveness by opening new pathways for market engagement, innovation and growth of the rural SMEs (Lekhanya, 2018, Liu et al., 2024). Complementary to that, the adoption and integration of digital technologies in rural SMEs will help in identifying and exploiting better business ventures, swiftly adapt to changes and broaden market reach in the business world (Liu et al., 2023, Liu et al., 2024). The digital shift alternatively helps the rural SMEs to mitigate the challenges emanating from institutional voids, hence providing the rural SMEs with the agility to address operational and structural limitations.

Digital technologies such as business process automation, AI algorithms, cyber security technologies, data mining, online payment systems and cloud computing are transforming rural SME owners' capabilities (Lukonga, 2020). These digital technologies are also equipping the owners of the rural SMEs with the adequate skills necessary for them to thrive in the evolving digital economic context. Digital technologies allow rural entrepreneurs to channel their enthusiasm into digital communication, actionable strategies, data-driven insights and utilisation of e-commerce platforms to differentiate and innovate their offerings (Luz, 2025, Manjon et al., 2022). Complementary to that, digital technologies foster an innovative and competitive business atmosphere, and rural SMEs can also flourish in the globally connected economy through the adoption and integration of digital technologies in businesses (Mbhele and Beharry-Ramraj, 2024b, Mbunge et al., 2022). Ultimately, the adoption and integration of digital technologies in rural SMEs nurture an entrepreneurship mindset marked by collaboration, learning and adaptability, which are crucial traits of growth and sustainability of the rural SMEs in KwaZulu-Natal. However, the competitiveness of the digital platforms

requires continuous upskilling, a robust policy on cybersecurity and sustainable funding (Meier et al., 2025). These requirements may also not be present in the context of the SMEs operating in rural areas. These systemic issues should be addressed; otherwise, failure to address these issues will result in digital enthusiasm not translating to sustainable competitiveness.

2.2.3 Leveraging Digital Practices to Unlock New Revenue Channels

Digital practices present rural SMEs with transformative convenient for the generation of new streams of revenue and supporting long-term growth. The development of digital technologies has reshaped rural SMEs by enhancing customer engagement, strategically positioning rural SMEs, and enabling access to untapped markets so that the businesses can compete at a global level (Meier et al., 2025, Moh'd-Anwer, 2024). Rural SMEs are empowered by digitalisation, hence they are able to interact with other businesses and customers in the national and international markets. These businesses interact in the national and international markets through various online platforms, making them more competitive and expanding their reach (Moh'd-Anwer, 2024, Mhlongo et al., 2024). The digital revolution is crucial for rural SMEs as much as it is for urban SMEs as they strive for sustainability. Digital technologies foster income-generating avenues for rural SMEs and communities as much as they foster business competitiveness. Complementary to that, the digital technologies revolution has facilitated digital networking through social media, mobile apps and e-commerce, optimising the performance of the business by facilitating partnerships and enabling greater market access (Muafi et al., 2021, Luz, 2025).

Digital transformation facilitates the automation and innovation of sales channels, supporting entrepreneurial flexibility and enhanced service delivery (Bollweg et al., 2020). As Lekhanya (2018) notes, digitalisation prompts rural SMEs to restructure their existing platforms or adopt new ones to meet evolving market demands. In that way, digital practices can empower rural SMEs in KZN to overcome traditional limitations, expand their market reach, and establish sustainable business models that support long-term development and competitiveness (Mutabazi, 2023). Nevertheless, studies have cautioned that digital income platforms are not silver bullets, especially if the entrepreneur lacks technical skills coupled with poor digital infrastructure to efficiently utilise digital platforms (Nadeem et al., 2020, OECD, 2019). This underscores the need for targeted digital capacity building and enabling environmental programmes.

2.2.4 Improving Access to Market Research, Business Data, and Networks through Digital Practices

Digital practices are transforming how rural SMEs obtain market research, business information, and networks, all of which are significant tools for informed decision-making and sustainable development as Bagale et al. (2021) argue that digital technologies allow rural entrepreneurs to access real-time, precise, and practical business data, which was previously not easy to obtain due to geographical and infrastructural constraints. By leveraging digital tools, rural SMEs can discover new data sources, obtain a deeper understanding of customer needs, and adjust their offerings accordingly (Paige, 2024, Oyeyemi et al., 2024, Agustian et

al., 2023). This data-driven method supports more focused product invention and customer interaction. Bag et al. (2022) and Rosário and Raimundo (2021) reinforce that market research is an important strategic component, providing insights into trends, competitor positioning, and consumer behaviour.

The digital revolution has transformed access to research, allowing rural entrepreneurs to employ sophisticated platforms and tools that elevate strategic planning and innovation (Prestidge, 2022). For rural SMEs, such access is chiefly valuable for recognising developing opportunities and mitigating possible risks associated with digital acceptance (Moh'd-Anwer, 2024, Singh et al., 2024). Data is often perceived as the currency of the digital economy, and for rural SMEs, real-time access to consumer trends, preferences, and buying behaviours is essential for survival and growth (Mutabazi, 2023, Agrawal, 2024). Digital platforms also enable entrepreneurs to collect, analyse, and act on large volumes of data, thereby improving decision-making and operational effectiveness (Mbunge et al., 2022, Vrontis et al., 2022). In addition to data access, digital technologies enable global virtual networking. These platforms link rural entrepreneurs with mentors, experts, associates, and prospective customers internationally, fostering partnership, innovation, and access to funding opportunities (Satakina and Steiner, 2020, Bereznoy et al., 2021).

Ultimately, the strategic application of digital resources enables rural SMEs to innovate more efficiently, access broader markets, and contribute substantially to the socio-economic development of rural communities (Soluk, 2021). Digital entrepreneurship, when implemented effectively, empowers rural SMEs to facilitate data-driven strategies that improve marketing accuracy, boost customer satisfaction, and foster business growth (Soluk et al., 2021). However, in the context of rural SMEs, language barriers and limited data literacy hinder the translation capacity of insights into efficient business strategies.

2.2.5 Expanding Reach and Reducing Costs through Digital Operational Functions

Digital practices offer cost-effective solutions for rural SMEs to expand their customer base and streamline client-facing operational functions such as advertising, communication, and distribution. These technologies promote reduced expenses usually associated with physical engagement while cultivating online customer interaction (Ritz et al., 2019, Ohara et al., 2024). As Sturgeon (2021) notes, the implementation of digital tools allows entrepreneurs to expand their market reach beyond local boundaries, connecting with customers, partners, and stakeholders across regional and global markets. Additionally, Holzmann and Gregori (2023) allude that digitalisation allows rural SMEs to overcome geographic constraints and access broader markets through platforms that support global visibility.

Rural entrepreneurs, like their urban counterparts, can leverage e-commerce websites, social media, and digital marketing tools to promote and sell their products and services to a wider audience, irrespective of location (Brahma and Dutta, 2020). This broader reach enables owners of rural SMEs to tap into new customer segments, penetrate global markets, and scale their operations more effectively (Abdul-Azeez et al., 2024). In addition to market reach, digital tools significantly decrease the cost of marketing and communications. Digital

marketing through social media, email campaigns, and search engines offers rural SMEs a cost-effective alternative to traditional marketing channels such as print or broadcast media (Lukonga, 2020). These methods not only lower operational costs but also allow for targeted messaging, improving the efficiency and impact of marketing efforts. Hence, the incorporation of digital technologies into day-to-day operations can enhance visibility, decrease expenditure, and attain more sustainable rural SME growth through improved outreach and operational efficacy (Muafi et al., 2021, Mutabazi, 2023). Nevertheless, if SMEs rely on digital marketing, there is a high chance of being exposed to new risks such as changes in the algorithm-driven platforms and cybersecurity threats. These risks are a disadvantage to the small business players who do not have digital marketing experience, as well as the funds to boost their business visibility.

2.2.6 Reducing Internal Operational Costs and Creating Electronic Value Through Digitalisation

By altering how companies function and interact with clients, digitalisation greatly improves value generation and overall performance for rural SMEs. It makes it possible to move towards value-driven and customer-centric models, where value is jointly produced by digital processes, system integration, and consumer contact (Elshaiekh et al., 2023). Rural SMEs may reach international markets, reduce operational and logistical expenses, and open up new opportunities for value delivery by using digital technology (Jayadatta, 2023). This shift to digital technology strengthens market position and boosts revenue by improving client experiences and operational efficiency. Further increasing the advantages of digitalisation for rural firms are technologies like social media and digital marketing, which provide affordable ways to increase sales and brand awareness (Lannone and Caruso, 2023, Mutabazi, 2023).

2.2.7 Strengthening Customer Relationships through Social Media

Social media has become a cornerstone of digital practices, significantly sharpening relations and interactions between the customers and the owners of rural SMEs. Social media platforms enable direct and interactive communication that nurtures relationship-building and customer engagement (Wibowo et al., 2020). By utilising social media channels, rural SMEs can cultivate their marketing strategies while promoting trust and loyalty among their customer base (Dwivedi et al., 2021, Jamil et al., 2022). Shared customer reviews and experiences have a great influence on the purchase decision to be made by the next customer; hence, social media is an influential tool (Mbhele and Beharry-Ramraj, 2024a). Additionally, Prestidge (2022) and Moh'd-Anwer (2024) allude that social media channels also enable SMEs to nurture relationships not only with customers but also with suppliers, potential investors, and strategic partners.

Social media benefits extend beyond enriching customer relations; rural SMEs can also enhance their brand value, increase awareness, and generate sales through cost-effective, highly targeted digital campaigns (Febrian et al., 2022, Tajvidi and Karami, 2021). Social media supports a wide range of business functions such as e-commerce, innovation, knowledge sharing, and product development (Bagale et al., 2021, Nadeem et al., 2020, Chuang, 2020).

Furthermore, Deel (2023) argues that social media enables businesses to humanise their brands, offer personalised communication, and harness the power of viral marketing, all of which are critical for SMEs aiming to thrive in a digital economy.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative research methodology using a survey research design to address the research questions. The approach was selected for its suitability in collecting standardised data from a large population and enabling statistical analysis of the results (Ghanad, 2023). A non-probability sampling method, quota and convenience sampling, was employed to select a representative sample of 383 owners and managers of formally registered rural SMEs from Harry Gwala, uMkhanyakude, and uMzinyathi KZN District Municipalities.

These District Municipalities were sampled due to their perceived high levels of rurality and socio-economic challenges. They are characterised by various disparities, including but not limited to persistent poverty, limited infrastructure, underdevelopment, and high unemployment rates. For example, the Harry Gwala District faces fragmented spatial development, poor service delivery, and limited economic opportunities (Harry Gwala District Municipality, 2021). Similarly, uMkhanyakude is sparsely populated, with significant rural-urban migration driven by unemployment (Nhlozi, 2023). The uMzinyathi District also experiences low urbanisation (16.6%), poor access to education and skills, and an unemployment rate of 29.5% (Department of Science and Technology, 2022). These contextual factors made the selected areas ideal for exploring how digital entrepreneurship supports rural SME development. Data from this representative sample was collected through a structured questionnaire that was designed in line with the literature conducted in this study to ensure validity and reliability.

The use of the quota sampling technique ensured that there was proportional representation of the rural SMEs across the three districts under study in KwaZulu-Natal. At the same time, the use of the convenience sampling technique addressed the problems associated with remote areas. The data on perceived impacts, innovation, digital technology use and demographics were collected using a structured questionnaire based on the literature and were tailored for rural SMEs. Likert scale items captured participants' digital technologies usage, perceptions and attitudes to ensure relevant and rich insights. The collected data were analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 29.0. Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were employed. Descriptive analysis included frequency distributions and tables, while inferential statistics enabled the researcher to conclude on the influence of digital entrepreneurship on rural SME development.

To uphold ethical standards, the study adhered to the Durban University of Technology's research ethics guidelines. Participants were provided with an information letter outlining the purpose of the study, their rights, and data confidentiality. They also received an informed consent form, which emphasised voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage without consequence.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Table 1

By adopting digitalization, entrepreneurs in our rural area can enable new digital customer services.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1,1	1,1	1,1
	Disagree	8	2,3	2,3	3,4
	Neutral	42	12,0	12,0	15,5
	Agree	172	49,3	49,3	64,8
	Strongly Agree	123	35,2	35,2	100,0
	Total	349	100,0	100,0	

As shown in **Table 1** above, the majority of the respondents (172 or 49.3%) agreed and (123 or 35.2%) further strongly agreed that through digital entrepreneurship, rural SME owners can adopt new digital customer services. A negligible proportion (42 or 12.0%) were neutral, (8 or 2.3%) disagreed, and (4 or 1.1%) strongly disagreed with the statement. The findings reveal that the respondents believed that adopting digital entrepreneurship in rural SMEs is essential because it allows owners of rural SMEs to tap into new digital customer services. A chi-square test was also conducted to test whether digital entrepreneurship enables new digital customer services. The results show ($X^2 = 318.006$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$) for this variable, indicating the influence of digital entrepreneurship in enabling new digital customer services and collaboration for rural SMEs. Consistently, Franco et al. (2021) contend that the adoption of digital entrepreneurship enables rural enterprises to adopt innovative digital customer services, as they are important for improving competitiveness and sustainability.

Table 2: Entrepreneurial Perceptions of Digitalisation as a Driver of Competitive Enthusiasm in Rural Areas

The use of digitalisation can ignite competitive enthusiasm from entrepreneurs in our rural area.					
		Frequency	Percent	X^2	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	0,9	270.441	0.001
	Disagree	19	5,4		
	Neutral	47	13,5		
	Agree	167	47,9		
	Strongly Agree	113	32,4		
	Total	349	100,0		

As indicated in **Table 2** above, a substantial number of respondents indicated that they agree (167 or 47.9%), followed by those who strongly agreed (113 or 32.4%) that the use of digitalisation can ignite competitive enthusiasm from entrepreneurs in rural areas. Subsequently, those that were neutral (47 or 13.5%) were followed by those that disagreed (19 or 5.4%) and those that strongly disagreed (3 or 0.9%) with the statement. These findings suggest that the respondents have confidence in the capacity of digital entrepreneurship to ignite their competitive enthusiasm. A chi-square test was also conducted for this variable to determine whether or not digital entrepreneurship influences igniting rural entrepreneurs' competitive enthusiasm. The results indicate ($X^2 = 270.441$; $df = 4$; $p = 0.001$), suggesting the potential influence digital entrepreneurship has in igniting rural entrepreneurs' competitive

enthusiasm. Moreover, Lannone and Caruso (2023) argue, digital tools have the potential to kindle entrepreneurial passion and competitiveness, preparing owners of rural SMEs with the competencies essential to flourish in a changing economic landscape.

Table 3: Digitalisation can assist entrepreneurs in our rural area to open new revenue channels

Digitalisation can assist entrepreneurs in our rural area to open new revenue channels.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	0,3	358.092	0.001
	Disagree	3	0,9		
	Neutral	43	12,3		
	Agree	182	52,1		
	Strongly Agree	119	34,1		
	Total	348	99,7		
Missing	System	1	0,3		
Total		349	100,0		

As shown in **Table 3** above, a considerable number of respondents agreed (182 or 52.1%), followed by those who strongly agreed (119 or 34.1%) that digitalisation has the potential to assist entrepreneurs to open new revenue channels. Sequentially, respondents that were neutral scored (43 or 12.3%), followed and a few respondents that disagreed (3 or 0.9%) and strongly disagreed (1 or 0.3%). These findings suggest that the respondents give credence to the potential influence digital entrepreneurship has in assisting owners of rural SMEs to open new revenue channels.

These results were also supported by the chi-square test that was conducted to determine whether or not digital entrepreneurship can assist owners of rural SMES to open new revenue channels. The results indicated that ($X^2 = 358.092$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$), confirming the potential influence of digital entrepreneurship in fostering rural SME owners to open new revenue channels that will assist them in attaining a broader market reach. Accordingly, Mutabazi (2023) alludes that digital technologies enable owners of rural SMES to tap into previously unreachable customer bases and foster sustainable growth.

Table 4: Respondents’ perceptions of digital entrepreneurship in enhancing access to market research, business data, and networks in rural communities

The adoption of digital entrepreneurship may improve access to market research, business data, and networks in our rural communities.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1,1	323.479	0.001
	Disagree	3	0,9		
	Neutral	43	12,3		
	Agree	163	46,7		
	Strongly Agree	136	39,0		
	Total	349	100,0		

As depicted in **Table 4** above, the results show that a significant portion of the respondents (163 or 46.7%) agreed and (136 or 39.0%) further agreed strongly that digital entrepreneurship

has the potential to help owners of rural SMES improve access to market research, business data, and networks. Subsequently, a lesser frequency of the respondents was neutral (43 or 12.3%), followed by strongly disagree (4 or 1.1%) and agree (3 or 0.9%). This means that a by and large proportion of the respondents, at 85.7%, perceived digital entrepreneurship as a catalyst to improve access to market research, business data, and networks.

The chi-square test was also conducted to determine the significance of this variable, and the results ($X^2 = 323.479$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$) confirmed its significance. These results suggest that digital entrepreneurship has the potential to enable owners of rural SMES to access market research, business data, and networks. These results are in line with the literature (Paige, 2024; Oyeyemi et al., 2024; Agustian *et al.*, 2023), indicating that through the adoption of digital entrepreneurship, rural SME owners can discover new data sources, acquire more knowledge about their customer needs, and adjust their offerings accordingly.

Table 5: Perceived Impact of Digitalisation on Expanding Reach and Reducing Client-Facing Operational Costs in Rural Areas

The adoption of digitalisation in our rural area can enhance a wider reach and lower cost of client-facing operational functions, e.g., advertising, communications, and distribution.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	0,9	345.542	0.001
	Disagree	3	0,9		
	Neutral	36	10,3		
	Agree	158	45,3		
	Strongly Agree	149	42,7		
	Total	349	100,0		

As illustrated in **Table 5** above, a significant proportion of the respondents either agreed (158 or 45.3%) or strongly agreed (149 or 42.7%) that digital entrepreneurship has a potential influence in assisting owners of rural SMES to enhance global reach and reduce cost for client-facing functions in their enterprises. Following this was a small quantity of the respondents who were neutral (36 or 10.3%), followed by those who disagreed and strongly disagreed (3 or 0.9%), respectively. A chi-square test was also administered to determine whether or not digital entrepreneurship has a potential influence in assisting owners of rural SMES to enhance global reach and reduce costs for client-facing functions. The results ($X^2 = 345.542$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$) indicated that there is a widely shared perception amongst the respondents regarding this variable. Overall, these findings suggest that there is a strong agreement amongst owners of rural SMES that digital entrepreneurship has a potential influence to assist owners of rural SMES to enhance a wider reach and lower cost of client-facing operational functions, such as advertising, communications, and distribution. These findings align with the perspectives of Ritz, Wolf, & McQuitty (2019), who believed that digital technologies promote online customer interaction while ensuring that costs associated with physical engagement are kept to a possible minimal extent. Similarly, Sturgeon (2021) argued, the implementation of digital tools has the potential to allow entrepreneurs to broaden their market reach beyond immediate boundaries, ensuring collaboration with customers, partners, and stakeholders across regional and global markets.

Table 1: Perceptions on the role of digital entrepreneurship in reducing internal operational costs and enabling electronic value creation in rural areas

The adoption of digital entrepreneurship in our rural area can lower the cost of internal operational functions and introduce electronic value creation.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	0,3	282.218	0.001
	Disagree	11	3,2		
	Neutral	53	15,2		
	Agree	162	46,4		
	Strongly Agree	122	35,0		
	Total	349	100,0		

As shown in **Table 6** above, most of the respondents agreed (162 or 46.6%) and strongly agreed (122 or 35.0%) that digital entrepreneurship has the potential influence in lowering the cost of internal operational functions and introducing electronic value creation. This was followed by those who were neutral (53 or 15.2%), disagreed (11 or 3.2%), and strongly disagreed (1 or 0.3%). These findings suggest that a by and large proportion of the respondents perceived digital entrepreneurship as an influential reagent that can lower the cost of internal operational functions and introduce electronic value creation for rural entrepreneurs. These findings are supported by a Chi-square test that was conducted to determine the influence of digital entrepreneurship in assisting owners of rural SMES in lowering costs on internal operational functions and introducing electronic value creation. The results show that ($X^2 = 282.218$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$) for this variable, indicating that this variable is significant, suggesting that digital tools have the potential to lower the cost of internal operational functions and introduce electronic value creation. These findings are consistent with (Moglia, Hopkins, & Bardoel, 2021; European Union, 2019) viewing digital entrepreneurship as a source of cost-effective strategies for business formation and management, including transitioning from traditional to hybrid or fully digital operations, enabling entrepreneurs to reduce financial burdens and logistical challenges.

Table 7: Perceived impact of digital platforms on enhancing customer relations through social media in rural entrepreneurship

The implementation of digital platforms in rural entrepreneurship can improve customer relations through social media.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	0,9	341.387	0.001
	Disagree	4	1,1		
	Neutral	36	10,3		
	Agree	148	42,4		
	Strongly Agree	158	45,3		
	Total	349	100,0		

As shown in **Table 7** above, most respondents agreed strongly (158 or 45.3% with the statement, followed by those who agreed (148 or 42.4%) that the implementation of digital platforms in rural entrepreneurship can improve customer relations through social media. Following those that were neutral (36 or 10.3%), disagree (4 or 1.1%), and strongly disagree

(3 or 0.9%) with the statement. These results show that rural SME owners believe that the adoption of digital entrepreneurship can inspire direct, real-time communication between businesses and their customers. A chi-square test was also conducted to determine whether digitalisation can influence the implementation of digital platforms by rural entrepreneurs to improve customer relations through social media. The results indicate the significance of this variable ($X^2 = 341.387$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$), suggesting that digitalisation can foster the implementation of digital platforms, which in turn will enhance customer relations through social networks. These findings are in line with Wibowo *et al.* (2020), perceiving social media as a platform that nurtures customer engagement as a result of direct interaction that takes place on social media platforms. Hence, literature suggests that through the use of social media platforms, owners of rural SMES can enhance their marketing strategies while maintaining trust and loyalty among their customer base (Ohara, Suparwata, & Rijal, 2024; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021; Jamil *et al.*, 2022)

Table 8: Respondents’ perceptions of digitalisation enhancing access to existing sales channels in rural entrepreneurship

Digitalisation can improve access to existing sales channels in rural entrepreneurship.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	0,3	316.799	0.001
	Disagree	5	1,4		
	Neutral	48	13,8		
	Agree	166	47,6		
	Strongly Agree	128	36,7		
	Total	348	99,7		
Missing	System	1	0,3		
Total		349	100,0		

As demonstrated in **Table 8** above, the majority of the respondents agreed (166 or 47.6%) and strongly agreed (128 or 36,7%) that the adoption of digital entrepreneurship can help owners of rural SMES improve access to their existing sales channels. Subsequently, a minimal proportion of the respondents were neutral (48 or 13.8%), followed by those who disagreed (5 or 1.4%), and strongly disagreed (1 or 0.3%) with the statement. The results indicate that rural SME owners believe in the potential influence digital entrepreneurship has in enabling owners of rural SMES to improve access to their existing sales channels. A Chi-square test was also administered to assess the significance of these findings. The results ($X^2 = 316.799$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$) for this variable confirmed that digitalisation has the potential influence in assisting owners of rural SMES to improve access to their existing sales channels. These results highlight that the adoption of digital tools will allow rural SME owners to access a broader market through digital technologies like e-commerce, social media, digital marketing, and online collaborations. These findings are consistent with the scoping literature (Doyle, 2016; Jin & Hurd, 2018; Nuseir, 2018), suggesting that Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) developments and social media influence engagements between businesses and consumers, through the use of digital communication tools, rural SMEs can engage with global suppliers, customers, and partners, making internationalisation more attainable and effective.

Table 9: Digitalisation can create new sales channels for rural enterprises

Digitalisation can create new sales channels for enterprises in our rural area.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	1	0,3	327.690	0.001
	Disagree	3	0,9		
	Neutral	49	14,0		
	Agree	171	49,0		
	Strongly Agree	124	35,5		
	Total	348	99,7		
Missing	System	1	0,3		
Total		349	100,0		

As portrayed in **Table 9** above, most of the respondents agreed (171 or 49.0%) and strongly agreed (124 or 35.5%) that digital entrepreneurship can enable owners of rural SMES to create new sales channels for their enterprises. This was followed by a relatively small number of respondents who posted neutral (49 or 14.0%), disagree (3 or 0.9%), and strongly disagree (1 or 0.3%). The findings indicate that owners of rural SMES believe that the adoption of digital entrepreneurship will potentially allow them to reach customers and markets that were previously inaccessible through traditional methods. A Chi-square test was conducted to determine whether or not digitalisation can help owners of rural SMES create new sales channels for their enterprises. The results indicated that ($X^2 = 327.690$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$), confirming the validity of the variable, suggesting that digitalisation can influence owners of rural SMES to create new sales channels for their enterprises. These findings are in line with Bollweg *et al.* (2020), indicating that among many other opportunities digitalisation bears, automation of new sales channels for secluded enterprises, including those that are operating in rural areas rural is at the top of the list.

Table 10: Perceived Role of Digitalisation in Developing and Transforming Platforms for Rural Enterprises

Adoption of digitalisation can develop new platforms and transform existing platforms for rural enterprises in our rural area.					
		Frequency	Percent	X ²	P-Value
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	0,9	363.494	0.001
	Disagree	3	0,9		
	Neutral	42	12,0		
	Agree	187	53,6		
	Strongly Agree	113	32,4		
	Total	348	99,7		
Missing	System	1	0,3		
Total		349	100,0		

As represented in **Table 10** above, a significant percentage of the respondents agreed (187 or 53.6%) and strongly agreed (113 or 32.4%) that adoption of digital entrepreneurship can foster the development of new platforms and transform existing platforms for rural enterprises. Followed by the neutral respondents (42 or 12.0%), those who disagreed (3 or 0.9%), and strongly disagreed (3 or 0.9%) with the statement. These findings show that the respondents

perceive and believe that digitalisation can facilitate the development of new platforms and transform existing platforms for rural enterprises. Accordingly, A Chi-square test that was conducted confirmed the significance of this variable. The results indicated that ($X^2 = 363.494$; $df = 4$; $P = 0.001$), suggesting that digitalisation is believed to have a potential influence in developing new platforms and transforming existing ones for rural enterprises. As also echoed by Lekhanya (2018), digitalisation has the potential to impose changes in methods used by rural SMEs in developing new platforms and transforming existing platforms.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to assess the role of digital entrepreneurship on the development of rural SMES in KwaZulu-Natal. The results indicated a potential influence of digital entrepreneurship on developing the entrepreneurship landscape in rural areas. A by and large proportion of the respondents (86.2%) projected their perceived influence of digital entrepreneurship as a potential strategy to open new revenue streams, as shown in Table 3. Again, as displayed in Table 9, most respondents (84.5%) indicated the potential influence of digital entrepreneurship in assisting rural SMES in developing new sales channels. Moreover, the respondents were predominantly (84.3%) optimistic that digital entrepreneurship can facilitate enhanced access to existing sales channels, as illustrated in Table 8. Notably, the influence of digital entrepreneurship was significantly portrayed in this study, even though digital entrepreneurship in many parts of rural areas is still scarce and affected by several factors, including a lack of digital infrastructure, digital illiteracy amongst rural entrepreneurs, and unavailability of broadband connectivity, hindering its potential. The overall impression is that owners of rural SMES are confident in the influence of digital entrepreneurship in helping rural SMES achieve business growth and sustainability, thereby thriving and flourishing in the present era of the 4th Industrial Revolution.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The influence of digital entrepreneurship has been lamented in this study, and therefore, for its potential to be realised in rural contexts, this study recommends the following.

6.1 Recommendations for Government

For rural SME owners to leverage the potential benefits digitalisation can offer, this study recommends that Government entities prioritise and implement programmes that facilitate the development of rural communities. Moreover, government initiatives such as the Township and Rural Entrepreneurship Programmes (TREP) intended to provide blended finance and business development support to various sectors in the rural and township economies with a view of promoting their participation in the mainstream economy should be distributed fairly (Department of Small Business Development: Republic of South Africa n.a). Additionally, the functionality of Government entities like the Small Enterprise Development and Finance Agency should be ensured across all small enterprises in SA, including those that are operating in rural areas. Ensuring the functionality of government entities is pivotal in developing rural SMEs as the services they are intended to offer can lead to the establishment of digital

infrastructure such as high-speed internet in rural areas which can assist rural entrepreneurs to overcome limited availability and reliability of mobile internet services, one of the key barriers to digital adoption in rural areas.

6.2 Recommendations for Policymakers

For policymakers, it is recommended that they work with local authorities or leaders to plan and develop policies for rural areas that will promote a conducive regulatory environment. Additionally, policymakers are encouraged to streamline administrative procedures, rules, and regulations that will accommodate rural SMES. It is also important that the criteria and compliance aspects are taken into consideration when these policies are formed. By fostering a conducive regulatory environment, rural entrepreneurs will be encouraged to partake in transformative initiatives such as digitising their business models, which will ultimately stimulate economic development.

6.3 Recommendations for Technology Development Agencies

For technology development agencies, it is recommended that before developing new technologies, they provide basic digital skills programmes and training to ensure digital awareness amongst rural inhabitants and entrepreneurs. This will not only improve their perception of digital technologies, but it will also spark a desire to use them. A collaborative effort between technology development agencies and rural entrepreneurs to devise practical strategies for the adoption of basic business technologies is also recommended. Such strategies should be designed to accommodate rural disparities; hence, they should be practical, cost-efficient, and easy to use. These can include mobile-based business technological tools that rural entrepreneurs and inhabitants can access using their mobile devices. Mobile internet should also be prioritised to ensure the effectiveness of these tools.

6.4 Recommendations for Rural Communities

For rural communities, it is recommended that community members take part in supporting the digitalisation of rural communities and SMEs alike. They need to participate in public digital awareness programmes conducted by government agencies and/or technology development agencies. Moreover, they need to form community forums that will enable a peer-to-peer support network for knowledge sharing and skill transfer.

Local leaders also need to do their part in encouraging community members to participate in these community initiatives; they also have a responsibility to raise digital awareness. These community-based initiatives will foster a supportive environment for both community members and SME owners trying to explore digitalisation.

6.5 Recommendations for Rural SME Owners

Lastly, this paper recommends that rural SME owners consider embarking on digitisation by adopting basic digital business tools that can streamline their business operations. This will expose them to many opportunities, including opening new revenue channels, improving access to existing sales channels and creating new sales channels. This will sharpen their digital skills. Moreover, they need to dedicate some time from their schedules to utilise free

educational platforms available on the internet, e.g. YouTube, TikTok, Artificial Intelligence tools, etc., for learning to stay informed about emerging digital trends. By putting in the effort towards the adoption of fully-fledged digital entrepreneurship, they can enhance their competitiveness and ensure long-term business development and sustainability.

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